

The Influence of Product Quality and Promotion on Purchase Decision through Price as a Variable Mediation of Sars-Cov2 Rapid Antigen at PT. Roche in Dkijakarta

Benedektus Wahyu Kusbiyantara
 Dr.DendiAnggiGumilang, SE., MM.
 Magister.Management,.FEB – University of MercuBuana

Abstract:- "The Influence of Product Quality and Promotion on Purchasing Decisions through Price as a Mediating Variable for Rapid Antigen Sars-Cov2 at PT Roche is the subject of this study. Quantitative research is used by the author in this study. The sample in this study are customers of PT. Roche as many as 156 respondents. Non-Probability Sampling is used as the sampling method in this study. Partial Least Square (PLS) is the tool of choice for analysis. The results of the study show that (1) product quality has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, (2) promotion has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, (3) product quality has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions significant effect on price, (4) promotion has a positive and significant effect on price, (5) price has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, (6) product quality has a positive effect and significant to decision.purchasing through price,(7)promotion has positive and significant to price positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions through price. According to the findings of this study, PT Roche should pay more attention to the wants and

needs of customers and find new ways to entice them to buy products.

Keywords:- Product Quality, Price, Promotion, Purchase Decision.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Research Background

It is known that the city of Wuhan in China is the origin of the new corona virus disease COVID-19. At the end of December 2019, the first case was found. Covid-19 quickly spread to humans and spread to a number of countries, including Indonesia, after that. The Indonesian government announced the first two positive cases of the Covid-19 virus spreading in Indonesia on March 2, 2020. It only took a short time for this virus to spread to almost all countries on this planet. Since then the government has implemented Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in various regions and tightened entry and exit points between regions and even between countries. The life cycle has been disrupted by the Covid-19 pandemic.

Fig. 1: 2020 Confirmed Positive Cases in Indonesia

In fact, the number of confirmed positive cases is increasing every day, as seen in the image below which depicts a saddle-like graph from 2020 to 2022. On February 16, 2022, there were 64,718 positive confirmed cases. As a

result, health procedures such as wearing masks, washing hands, and maintaining distance when leaving the house must still be carried out.

Fig. 2: Graph of Average Increase in Positive Cases per Day

Based on data as of 2 February 2022, there were 94,109 active cases of Covid-19 in Indonesia, according to the Covid-19 Handling Task Force Report. As shown in the

image below, DKI Jakarta is recorded as the most active contributor of Covid-19 cases with a total of 41,818 cases:

Fig. 3: 10 Provinces in Indonesia with the Most Active Cases of Covid-19

The Covid-19 pandemic is getting under control in Indonesia over time and in recent months. On December 27, 2022, there were 1.7 daily cases of Covid-19 per 100,000 people, a weekly positive rate of 3.35 percent, a hospitalization rate of 4.79 percent, and a death rate of 2.39 percent. All of these meet WHO standards, and all districts

and cities in Indonesia currently have PPKM level 1, or low crowd and movement restrictions.

The government decided to revoke the PPKM contained in the Minister of Home Affairs Instructions number 50 and 51 of 2022 after reviewing and considering these developments for approximately ten months.

Fig. 4: Revocation of PPKM by the President of Indonesia

Namun, kemungkinan virus Covid-19 tetap ada meski PPKM dicabut. Hal tersebut menunjukkan bahwa masih terdapat virus Covid-19 di Indonesia, khususnya di DKI Jakarta berdasarkan data

terkini. Berdasarkan informasi yang diperoleh dari <http://corona.jakarta.go.id/id/data-pemantauan> antara 1 Januari 2022 sampai dengan 31 Januari 2023, berikut update terbaru kasus positif terkini:

Fig. 5: The Latest Update on the DKI Jakarta Covid-19 Daily Case Report

Antigen tests are still being offered by a number of health facilities to find out whether or not the Covid-19 virus is present, even though positive cases of the virus continue to decrease every year.

One company that offers a SARS-COV2 antigen test that has high sensitivity and specificity, good sterility, and is easy to use is PT Roche.

The Ministry of Health has granted official distribution permits to at least three brands of Rapid Test Antigen: PT Roche, PT Abbott and PT Diagnostik Standard and the following is the estimated sales data:

Fig. 6: sales data (in billions)

It can be seen from the sales data in the image above that PT Roche is the market leader with sales of 124 million in 2019, 9.241 billion in 2020, and 19.128 billion in 2021. PT Abbott is in second place and PT SD is in third. However, sales of rapid reagents also experienced a significant decline when positive cases of Covid-19 began to decline in mid-2022.

The author's information from the e-catalog website regarding the price range for rapid tests reveals that PT Roche's rapid test prices are more expensive than other test brands but PT Roche is still the market leader, along with the price range:

Company	Brand	Packaging	Price (Rp)
PT. Roche	SARS-CoV-2	25 test	2.160.000
PT. Abbott	BioQuick	25 test	1.950.000
PT. SD	Biosensor	25 test	2.000.000

Table 1: Rapid Antigen Price Range Data

Based on the information in the table above, the SARS-CoV-2 rapid test is more expensive compared to other brands of rapid tests. But with the high price offered, PT. Roche guarantees product quality with a sensitivity of 96.52% and a specificity of 99.68%, PT Roche guarantees excellent product quality.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Product Quality

Products are everything that can or is able to offer producers to the market to be requested, searched for, purchased, used, or consumed by the market to satisfy their needs and wants (Putri, 2017). This includes personal items, services, places, organizations, ideas, and physical objects.

Meanwhile, Kotler & Armstrong experts stated (in Andre ErlindoSyam, 2022), that is, product quality is a very important strategy to compete with competitors. Customers are more likely to make a purchase when a product is of higher quality.

B. Promotion

According to Laksana (2019), promotion is communication between sellers and buyers based on correct information and aims to change the attitudes and behavior of buyers who were previously unconscious to become familiar

so that they become buyers and always remember the product.

C. Price

Price, according to BashuSwastha (in Adelia and Nasution et al., 2020), is the amount of money (plus, if possible, several products) required to obtain various combinations of products and services.

"Price is the value of an item expressed in money," said Alma H. Buchari (2018).

D. Purchase Decision

According to Armstrong and Kotler (2018: 158), consumers make many daily purchases, which are the main focus of marketers' efforts. To answer questions about what consumers buy, where they buy, how much they buy, when they buy, and why they buy, most of the big companies conduct in-depth research on consumer buying decisions in Indonesia..

Fig. 7: Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research Design

A series of samples and numerical data are used in this type of research, which takes a quantitative approach (Sugiyono, 2017). In addition, this research is associative in nature, which aims to ascertain the impact of two or more variables. The purpose of this research is to find out whether the independent variables are effective: product quality, promotion, price and dependent variable: decision to purchase PT Roche's SARS-COV2 rapid antigen in DKI Jakarta.

B. Population and Sample

Sugiyono emphasized (2019: 126), population is a generalization area which includes: objects or subjects that have been selected by researchers to study and then analyzed to arrive at a number of established conclusions. All customers from hospital agencies, clinical laboratories, or students participated in this study, especially the purchasing department and laboratory staff who had previously used PT. PT. Roche.

The Slovin formula, which is the formula for calculating the minimum number of samples if the population is known, this Slovin formula is used by researchers to determine the number of samples:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Wichone:

n = Sample Size

N = Population Size

e = Tolerance limits error (error tolerance).

The Slovin formula can be used to determine sample size based on the previous explanation:

$$n = \frac{468}{1+(468 \times 0,05^2)} = 156$$

A. Responden Respondent Descriptive Analysis

➤ Base on Gender

Based on the characteristics, there are 98 male respondents (67%) and 58 female employees (33%).

➤ Base on Age

Based on their characteristics, 45 respondents (29%) were aged between 20 and 30, 69 respondents (43%) were between 31 and 40, 27 respondents (18%) were between 41 and 50, and the rest of the respondents were over the age of 51 (or 10%). This shows that the majority of research respondents were between 31 and 40 years old.

✓ Convergent Validity Test Results

• Product Quality

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Note
Product Quality (X1)	K1	0,812	Valid
	K2	0,739	Valid
	K3	0,807	Valid
	K4	0,644	Valid

Table 2: Product Quality

• Promotion

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Note
Promotion (X2)	P1	0,742	Valid
	P2	0,965	Valid
	P3	0,887	Valid

Table 3: Promotion

• Price

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Note
Price (Y1)	H1	0,773	Valid
	H2	0,768	Valid
	H3	0,896	Valid

Table 4: Price

156 respondents from purchasing department staff, purchasers, and laboratory staff in hospitals and laboratories were involved in this study, as indicated by the sample size calculation above. A non-probability sampling technique was used to select the sample. The technique of determining the sample is a non-probability sampling method. Purposive sampling is a type of non-probability sampling technique used.

Customers who have used the SARS-COV2 rapid antigen reagent product and institutions that have used the product are the sample selection criteria. Respondents between the ages of 20 and 55 because at that age can provide clear and reliable data for evaluation.

IV. RESULT RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

➤ Base on Function

Civil servants were 73 respondents (42%), private employees were 40 respondents (36%), students were 35 respondents (17%) and others were 8 respondents (5%). Civil servants are the most respondents.

B. Instrument Test Analysis

➤ Outer Model Analysis

• Validity Test

If the correlation between each indicator is greater than 0.70, it is considered valid. Scale development research, on the other hand, found that a loading factor of 0.50 to 0.60 is acceptable.

- Purchase Decision

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Note
Purchase Decision (Y2)	KP1	0,981	Valid
	KP2	0,822	Valid
	KP3	0,859	Valid

Table 5: Purchase Decision

- Descriminant Validity Test Result

	Product Quality	Promotion	Price	Purchase Decision
K1	0,812	0,342	0,198	0,053
K2	0,739	0,637	0,444	0,143
K3	0,807	0,708	0,678	0,280
K4	0,644	0,516	0,448	0,273
P1	0,280	0,742	0,319	0,283
P2	0,492	0,965	0,551	0,299
P3	0,295	0,887	0,378	0,151
H1	0,601	0,227	0,773	0,206
H2	0,557	0,325	0,768	0,458
H3	0,611	0,652	0,896	0,339
KP1	0,481	0,327	0,210	0,981
KP2	0,346	0,296	0,286	0,822
KP3	0,251	0,664	0,140	0,859

Table 6: Descriminant Validity Test Result

Based on the table above, there is a stronger correlation between the Product Quality construct and its indicators than between the Product Quality indicators and other constructs. In addition, there is a stronger correlation between Promotion and the indicator than between the

indicator and the other constructs. The correlation of price indicators with other constructs is lower than the correlation of price indicators with other constructs. In addition, there is a stronger correlation between the Purchasing Decision indicator and its indicators compared to the other constructs.

- Average Variance Extracted (AVE)Tets

Variable	AVE
Product Quality	0,823
Promotion	0,836
Price	0,785
Purchase Decision	0,849

Table 7: Average.Variance.Extracted (AVE)Tets

- FornellLackerCriterium Test

	Product Quality	Promotion	Price	Purchase D
Product Quality	0,825			
Promotion	0,672	0,836		
Price	0,748	0,759	0,874	
Purchase Decision	0,809	0,827	0,833	0,881

Table 8: FornellLackerCriterium Test

- Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha Test

Variable	Composite Reliability	Cornbach's Alpha	Note
Product Quality	0,719	0,827	Reliabel
Promotion	0,804	0,856	Reliabel
Price	0,836	0,824	Reliabel
Purchase Decision	0,865	0,871	Reliabel

Table 9: Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha Test

Because all latent variables have a reliable composite value and Cronbach's alpha 0.70, the combined reliability and Cronbach's alpha test gives satisfactory results. This means that all latent variables are reliable.

➤ Inner Model Analysis

• R-Square Value Test Results

Endogen Variable	R-square
Price	0,834
Purchase Decision	0,857

Table 10: R-Square Value Test Results

Because the value is greater than 0.67, the variable model. Price and Purchase Decision can be said to be strong. The R-square value of the model of the effect of independent latent variables (Product Quality and Promotion) on price indicates that the construct variability of Price is 83.4 percent explained by the construct variability of Product Quality and Promotion, while 16.6 percent is explained by variables other than those being studied. The R-square value of the influence model. independent latent variable. (Quality.Product, Promotion, and.Price).to.Purchasing Decisions of 0.857, indicating that 85.7% of the variability of the construct of Purchase Decisions can be explained by Product Quality, Promotion, and Price. Price construct variability, while 14.3% can be explained by other variables not studied.

• Goodness ofFit Model Test Result

The Predictive-relevance (Q2) value is used to test the Goodness of Fit on the inner model with the structural model. The model has a predictive relevance value when the Q-value is greater than (0) zero. The following is the calculation of the R-square value of each endogenous variable in this study:

The predictive relevance value is obtained by the formula:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R_1) (1 - R_p)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0,834)(1 - 0,857)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (0,166)(0,143)$$

$$Q^2 = 0,976$$

The calculation above produces a predictive-relevance value of 0.976 which is greater than 0 (zero). This shows that the independent variable used is 97.6% of the variation in the dependent variable, Price and Purchase Decision; consequently, the model is considered feasible and has relevant predictive value.

• Hipotesis Test Result

The value of the structural model estimates for path relationships must be significant. The bootstrapping method can be used to determine the significance of this hypothesis. Check the significance value of the bootstrapping algorithm report and the parameter coefficient values to determine the significance of the hypothesis. The T-table is compared with the T-count (T-statistics) to determine whether it is significant or not at an alpha of 0.05 (5 percent = 1.96).

	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Note
Product Quality > Purchase Decision	0,312	0,272	2,517	0,002	Positive– Significant
Promotion > Purchase Decision	0,263	0,318	3,186	0,001	Positive – Significant
Product Quality > Price	0,327	0,297	3,375	0,001	Positive – Significant
Promotion > Price	0,338	0,369	3,804	0,004	Positive – Significant
Price > Purchase Decision	0,374	0,386	3,776	0,003	Positive - Significant

Table 11: Hipotesis Test Result

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusions

Base on the research conducted at PT. Roche, .then.can be drawn.conclusion.as.following:

- Quality.Product. has a positive and significant effect on.Decisions.Purchasing PT. Roche. Means if the quality of the product is good then the level of purchasing decisions will also be better.
- Promotion has a positive and significant effect on PT. Roche. This means that if the promotion of an item goes well, the level of purchasing decisions will also be better.
- Product quality has a positive and significant effect on the price of PT. Roche. This means that if the quality of

the product is good, the price offered will be more expensive according to the quality of the product being sold.

- Promotion has a significant positive effect on the price of PT. Roche. This means that if the promotion presented by the company is good and convincing, the price offered will be even more expensive according to the quality of the product being sold.
- Price has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions of PT. Roche. This means that if the price offered by the company is in accordance with the ability of consumers, the level of consumer purchasing decisions will also increase.

- Product Quality has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decisions through PT. Roche. This means that if the quality of the product and the price offered matches what the consumer wants, then the level of consumer purchasing decisions will also increase.
- Promotion has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions through the price of PT. Roche. This means that if the promotion presented is convincing, attractive and the price is in accordance with the ability of the consumer, then the consumer's purchasing decision will also increase.

B. Suggestion

➤ For PT. Roche :

- Management and leaders must be able to make something new or innovate SARS-COV2 reagent products, so that consumers feel interesting and not bored with the products offered.
- Management and leaders should make product promotions for SARS-COV2 reagents with attractive designs and pictures so that consumers are increasingly interested in buying RASR-COV2 reagents.
- Management and leadership should consider determining the price offered by consumers, so that consumers are not too burdened with the price offered.
- Management and leadership should be more observant in determining the products consumers need, so that if consumers buy the products being sold it will not be in vain if they are in accordance with their needs.

➤ For further researchers :

Suggestions for future researchers, preferably those who will use this thesis as a reference and conduct research in the same field. This thesis needs to be reviewed again because it does not rule out the possibility that there are statements that are not appropriate. As a writer, I believe there are still many shortcomings and limitations in completing this thesis.

In addition, future researchers must be able to create new indicators and variables that are not used in this study.

➤ For academics:

For academics and readers to consider additional factors that influence purchasing decisions, such as location, perceived price, brand image, etc., to broaden the research.

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